

DETERMINING AND ASSESSING THE POPULATION'S ATTITUDE TOWARDS ECOLOGISTS

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Abstract

The article is about the determination and analysis of the population's attitude to volunteers and specialists working in the field of ecology and interested in nature protection based on a special survey. The research was carried out in the form of a questionnaire, for five days, using the "Telegram" messenger. According to the results of the anonymous survey, 355 people read the questionnaires, but more than 149 people (42%) actively answered the survey questions.

Key words: Ecologist, nature-loving volunteer, eco-activist, ecological education, ecological activity.

Ecologist – one who advocates for the protection of the environment and biosphere from misuse from human activity through such measures as ecosystem protection, waste reduction and pollution prevention [1]. Ecologists are persons who play an important role in nature protection. Their salary should be sufficient for all the needs of the specialist. Ecologist's average monthly salary in US is \$ 4,888 [2], for Germany is 5,710 € [3], in Uzbekistan, the monthly salary for ecologists is 1.5 million sums (more than 100 \$) (2022) [4]. In addition, the reputation and position of the environmentalist in the society should be high.

Below are the results of a small research conducted in order to check and analyze the attitude of our people to ecologists. The research was conducted in the form of a questionnaire. "Telegram" messenger was used for this purpose. The research was conducted anonymously for 5 days, consisting of 5 questions, two or three different answers, and 355 people got acquainted with the electronic questionnaire directly, of which 42% (149 people) answered the questions. 58% (206 people) of those who got acquainted with the questionnaire did not answer the questionnaire questions (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Inactive (58 %) and active (42 %) participants

As it can be seen from the results of the analysis, the weight of those who are not interested in the topic of the questionnaire is high, which proves the low level of ecological culture and ecological knowledge.

The first question of the survey, that is, "Do you think that those who work in the field of ecology are paid a satisfactory salary?" 156 people answered the question, of which 19% answered "Yes", 41% answered "No", and 40% answered "I don't know" (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

The second question of the survey, that is, "Do you think that the financial and spiritual support of ecologists and nature conservation volunteers is also a form of caring for nature?" 147 people answered the question, of which 67% answered "Yes", 18% answered "No", and 15% answered "I don't know" (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The third question of the survey, that is, "What is the position of ecologists and nature activists in society?" 148 people answered the question, of which 15% answered "High", 39% answered "Very low", 46% answered "Normal" (Figure 4).

Figure 4.

The fourth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Would you support if your child wishes to become an environmentalist in the future?" 147 people answered the question, of which 55% answered "Yes", 45% answered "No" (Figure 5).

Figure 5.

The fifth question of the anonymous survey, that is, "Would you personally like to help nature lovers and environmentalists?" 149 people answered the question, of which 73% answered "Yes", 11% answered "No", and 16% answered "Sometimes" (Figure 6).

Figure 6.

Analyzing the results of the survey, the following conclusions can be drawn. Most of our people did not want to be active, which is a sign of lack of interest in environmental issues. A large percentage of respondents think that ecologists' monthly salary is low and expressed the need to support environmentalists and eco-activists. Most of the participants think that the reputation of ecologists is normal in society. The percentage of respondents who believe and support that their children will become environmental specialists in the future is high. A large percentage of respondents indicated that they always want to personally help ecologists.

Использованная литература:

- [1] <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/ecologist>
- [2] <https://www.indeed.com/career/ecologist/salaries>
- [3] <http://www.salaryexplorer.com/salary-survey.php?loc=81&loctype=1&job>
- [4] <http://kun.uz/54795553>

